

8T – The Multiverse is Continuous and Discrete

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the main two equations of the 8T – author analyzes the continuous aspects of the universe alongside the discrete aspects – manifested in prime amount of curvatures associated with the primordial and the fact that the universe packet has a discrete amount of manifolds – could be described in a graph if we could correlate each new manifold to the one it was emerged from due to matrix tensor fluctuations .

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equation (1.2). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. By analyzing equation (1.1) to (1.2) it is vividly clear that the setting is continuous, we have a smooth manifold which is the connected manifold. As both 8T and Einstein GR are composed upon a continuous (3,1) matric tensor. However, 8T is also discrete in a sense that the Bosons are associated with discrete amounts of curvature, prime or one, in their nature. That was the idea that led to the discovery of the primordial coupling series. So taken from that point of view the universe has an element that is discrete. This element comes to an agreement with the fundamental Planck constant, which states that the Quantum oscillator can change only by discrete amounts. Therefore, the 8T setting is continuous, but this continuous setting has certain quantities that are discrete and are of grand importance. Another element that could be regarded as discrete is the number of universes in the packet. It is possible to regard, and maybe it is even the case, to each newborn manifold in the packet as a descended of a more ancient manifold in the packet, which was born due to matric tensor fluctuations. Classification can be made based upon the location in the packet. It is possible (theoretically that is) to numerate the manifolds in the packet, assuming it is finite but still aspiring infinity. That is an additional element which is discrete, despite each manifold is continuous.

So based on this short analysis of the main two equations of the framework 8T, we have a mixture of both continuous setting, given by infinite smooth manifolds interacting with each other, and at the same time, discrete features such as prime numbers, isomorphic to Bosonic fields and discrete number of universes in the packet – which could be described as a graph if we can correlate the newborn manifolds to those they emerged from.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)